

Review Article on Synthesis and Applications of Thiosemicarbazides and Their Derivatives Like Thiadiazoles and Triazoles with Traditional Methods as Well as Green Protocols

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ABSTRACT

The greener route for the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds plays an important role in the field of organic synthesis from last two decades. Substituted semicarbazides have attracted much attention due to their diverse biological, industrial and agricultural importance. The intramolecular dehydrative cyclization reaction of thiosemicarbazides in basic or acidic media gives 1,2,4-triazoles and 1,3,4-thiadiazoles respectively. The term sonochemistry is used to describe the effect of ultrasound waves on chemical reactivity. A number of reviews on the chemical applications of ultrasound have been published. Microwave-assisted reactions also have gained popularity as they provide an opportunity to work with open vessels and an enhanced possibility of upscaling the reaction on a preparative scale. In this reaction time has been brought down from hours to seconds. The problems associated with waste disposal of solvents and excess chemicals have been overcome by performing reactions with small amount of solvent or without solvent under ultrasound or microwave irradiation. With easy availability of ultrasound and microwave sources, their use in chemistry has gained momentum. In these environmentally conscious days, the developments in the technology are directed towards environmentally sound and cleaner procedures.

Keywords: Thiosemicarbazides, 1,2,4-triazoles, 1,3,4-thiadiazoles, Green protocols.

INTRODUCTION

The chemistry of thiosemicarbazides and semicarbazides have attracted much attention in recent years due to their broad-spectrum biological activities and as an important intermediate in the preparation of the corresponding semicarbazides metal complexes and heterocyclic compounds.¹⁻³

Thiosemicarbazides are important compounds because of their reported industrial use and biological activities like anti-convulsant,⁴ anti-fungal,⁵ plant growth promoting⁶ and anti-bacterial.⁷ Thiosemicarbazides are used as intermediates for the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds such as 1,2,4-triazole,⁸ 1,3,4-thiadiazoles⁹ and 1,3,4-oxadiazoles¹⁰ derivatives.

During the last decade microwave methodology and solvent free experiment have been carried out in organic synthesis.¹¹ Microwave-assisted reactions have gained popularity as they provide an opportunity to work with open vessels and an enhanced possibility of upscaling the reaction on a preparative scale.¹² In this reaction time has been brought down from hours to seconds with improved yield using solid supports coupled with MWI as compared to conventional heating.¹³ The use of ultrasonic waves to promote reaction is now a recognized field of chemistry.^{14,15} The phenomenon of cavitation seems to be the origin of the sonochemical effects and the physical phenomenon, high temperature or electric fields, taking place during cavitation are able to cleave many bonds, mainly homolytically. Thus, the sonochemistry is the preferential domain of radicals, radical ions and single electron transfer (SET).

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Review of Some synthetic Methods

Khosrow Zamani and coworkers¹⁶ reported the synthesis of thiosemicarbazides by reaction of substituted pyridine carboxylic acid hydrazides with

4-methyl phenyl isothiocyanate which through intramolecular cyclization gives 1,2,4-triazoles and 1,3,4-thiadiazoles.

Floch L et al¹⁷ reported the synthesis of novel heterocycles derived from α -amino acid to give 3-aminothiohydantoin via thiosemicarbazides.

Thiosemicarbazides are easily cyclized by the action of acids, bases or oxidants, therefore they are useful versatile building blocks for the preparation of heterocyclic ring systems.¹⁸ Hassan A A et al investigated the reactions of thiosemicarbazides with pi-deficient compounds, which gives many heterocyclic ring system such as thiazoles, thiadiazoles, thiadiazines, pyrazines and indazoles.^{19,20}

In general, 3,4-disubstituted 1,2,4-triazole could be prepared by the intramolecular dehydrative cyclization of 1,4-disubstituted thiosemicarbazides.

The intramolecular dehydrative cyclization reaction of thiosemicarbazides in basic or acidic media was used for the construction of 1,2,4-triazole and 1,3,4-thiadiazole heterocyclic rings respectively.²¹ The substituted 1,2,4-triazole nucleus is particularly common and examples can be found in marketed drugs such as fluconazole,²² terconazole,²³ rizatriptan,²⁴ alprazolam and triazolam.

Zamani K and co-workers²¹ were synthesized derivatives of 1,2,4-triazoles and 1,3,4-thiadiazole from intramolecular dehydrative cyclization reaction of thiosemicarbazides by using acidic or basic media.

1,2,4-TRIAZOLE

1,3,4-THIADIAZOLE

Wang X C and coworkers²⁵ reported synthesis of 1,4-diacyl semicarbazides using 1,4-diacyl thiosemicarbazides as a starting material and potassium iodate as reagent. Thiosemicarbazides

were prepared from reaction of 4-chlorobenzoyl chloride with ammonium thiocyanate first, then with aryloxyacetic acid hydrazides in the presence of polyethylene glycol-400, at room temperature give 1-aryloxyacetyl-4-(4-chlorobenzoyl) thiosemicarbazides.

Cyclopropanones undergo several interesting cycloaddition reactions with thiosemicarbazides.²⁶

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Jagadhani S.G. and co-workers²⁷ reported the synthesis of thiosemicarbazide derivatives by using benzoxazole moiety by conventional and non-conventional methods.

Substituted 1,2,4-triazoles and the *N*-bridged heterocyclic compounds derived from them have received considerable attention in last two decades as potential antimicrobial agents.²⁸⁻³¹

Jayachandran E and co-workers³² synthesized substituted fluoropyrazolo (3,4-*d*) triazoles and screened them for antibacterial and antifungal activity.

Sire et al³³ synthesized 1, 2, 3- triazoles from nitroalkenes. Nitroalkenes or vicinal acetoxy nitro derivatives undergo a clean reaction with sodium

azides in hot dimethyl sulfoxide to give the corresponding 1, 2, 3-triazoles in good yields.

Sayed R E described the use of 1,2,4-triazole derivatives³⁴ as a starting material for the synthesis of some important biologically active heterocycles.

Karale B K and co-workers has synthesized triazoles from 1-(2-benzo[*d*]isoxazol-3-yl)-acetyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazides ²⁷ on treatment with 2N

NaOH by Conventional, Microwave and ultrasonication method.

Substituted **1,3,4-thiadiazoles** are very useful compounds in medicine, agriculture and many fields of technology.³⁵ A large number of 1,3,4-thiadiazoles

have been patented in the agricultural field as herbicides,³⁶ fungicides³⁷ and bacteriocides.³⁸ In the medical field one of the best known drugs based on a 1,3,4-thiadiazole is acetazolamide (acetazola).³⁹

Different derivatives of 1,3,4-thiadiazole containing substituted amino, thiophene-3-carboxylic acids are found to contain analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity.⁴⁰

Wei T B and co-workers reported the synthesis of 2,5-disubstituted 1,3,4-thiadiazoles by the cyclization of 1-acyl-4-arylthiosemicarbazides. These reactions were carried out in acetic acid under the conditions of microwave irradiation.³⁵

Tayade et al⁴¹ synthesized biologically active 1,2,4-thiadiazoles by the interaction of guanidine with various alkyl or arylisothiocyanates under different

reaction conditions and medium for isolation of **1** and **2**. Which on further oxidation were successfully converted in to 1,2,4-thiadiazoles.

Akhtaruzzaman M and co-workers⁴² synthesized 2,1,3-benzothiadiazole derivatives by using the Sonogashira cross-coupling reaction of 4,7-dibromo-

2,1,3-benzothiadiazole with the corresponding ethynylpyridines in the presence of a Pd(II) catalyst.

Zhang S et al⁴³ synthesized derivatives like 2,5-di(m-tolylcarbamoyl-methylthio)-1,3,4-thiadiazole.

1,2,3-Thiadiazole derivatives are useful in the treatment of hyperproliferative disorders including tumor growth and angiogenesis and lymphoproliferative symptoms.⁴³

Zaleska B et al⁴⁴ reported the novel route to synthesise 1,2,3-thiadiazole derivatives.

Okuma K et al⁴⁵ reported the synthesis of **2** i. e. 2,5-di(p-tolyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole by the reaction of **1** p-tolualdehyde hydrazone with disulfer dichloride in

presence of DBU (1,8-diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undec-7-ene) as a base.

Cheng D P and co-workers⁴⁶ reported a facile synthesis of 3,5-disubstituted 1,2,4-thiadiazoles by oxidative dimerization of thioamides using polymer supported iodobenzene diacetate. The advantages of

polymer-supported reactive species are now widely recognized by organic chemistry and the exploitation of these systems is developing both in academic and industrial laboratories.⁴⁷

Krishna B G and co-workers⁴⁸ synthesized 1,3,4-thiadiazole derivatives containing benzoxazole

moiety which shows significant anti-inflammatory activity.

Karale B K and co-workers has synthesized thiadiazoles from 1-(2-benzo[*d*]isoxazol-3-yl)-acetyl)-4-aryl thiosemicarbazides²⁷ on treatment with

Conc. H₂SO₄ by Conventional, Microwave and ultrasonication method.

Compounds having 1,2,3-triazole nucleus have been reported as antibacterial,⁴⁹ sedative, anti-convulsant,^{50,51} anti-inflammatory⁵² agents they also reported as potent heterocycles with antifungal and antitubercular activity.⁵³

Jayachandran E and co-workers⁵⁴ synthesized substituted fluoropyrazolo (3,4-*d*) triazoles and screened them for antibacterial and antifungal activity.

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